

Introduction

Dear Participant(s),

Congratulations! You have passed the screening survey and are qualified to take our study on understanding how programming-related articles on online platforms are evaluated (e.g., how developers evaluate tech blogs). Thank you for your participation! In this study, we will only ask you to take this following survey which should take less than 10 minutes.

In this survey, to keep the survey at a reasonable length, only the title and the first paragraph of the article are shown for evaluation. This survey has a total of 7 articles with 3 questions each that should be answered based on a target question that would be provided.

At the end of the survey, there will be a short demographic survey. The demographic data will only be used for statistical purposes, and no personally identifiable information will be collected or linked to the results of this survey.

Thank you again for your participation!

If you have any questions during or after the study, please contact Anda Liang via emails: anda.liang@vanderbilt.edu. You are free to withdraw from the study anytime you want. You will get a \$3 payment upon the completion of the study.

*If you are redirected to this survey from MTurk, at the end of the survey, you will receive a unique code for your response. Please enter your code on the MTurk platform to show your completion of the survey. You will receive the payment of \$3 within 5 business days from the time of completion.

*If you are redirected to this survey from receiving the email from the Vanderbilt mailing list, you will be contacted by the research team for your payment of \$3 via emails within 5 business days.

118

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some advantages of Cloudmersive Image

API when compared to other image processing tools?

Rotate an Image in Python

by Amanda

Setting up your very own image editing app or automated flow? The Cloudmersive Image API can be a big help, providing important photo-editing services among its suite of useful iterations. Using the Rotate Image iteration of the Image API (`/image/edit/rotate/{degrees}/angle`), you can rotate an image any number of degrees (values range from 0.0 to 360.0) in a few simple steps.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

Extremely unlikely Somewhat unlikely Neither likely nor unlikely Somewhat likely Extremely likely

This article contains an answer to the target question.

How in-depth do you think the article will be on its intended topic based on the first paragraph?

Extremely superficial Somewhat superficial Neither superficial nor in-depth Somewhat in-depth Extremely in-depth

How in-depth is this article?

How would you rate the understandability of this writing based on its first paragraph?

Extremely easy Somewhat easy Neither easy nor difficult Somewhat difficult Extremely difficult

How is the understandability of this article?

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the steps for creating a 3D model based on a 2D image?

OpenCV python library for processing multimedia files

by Hannah

Analyzing three-dimensional data from two-dimensional images based on unnecessary noise removal, geometric transformation, contrast enhancement, and edge detection methods. Let's start installing the OpenCV python library from jupyter notebook.

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116

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some security vulnerabilities that the previous version of Dart SDK had?

Dart 2.16: Improved tooling and platform handling

by Jessica

Today the Dart SDK version 2.16 is available. It has no new language features, but a bunch of bug fixes (including a fix for a security vulnerability), improved support for specifying the platforms that Dart packages support, and a brand new search experience for pub.dev.

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121

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How is back propagation implemented in neural networks?

Training of Neural Networks — Back Propagation

by Michael

Neural Networks are used in Deep Learning Algorithms. A neural network consists of different layers. The first layer is the input layer, the second is the various hidden layers, and finally the output layer. Initially, the input layer consists of all features that need to be passed to the neural network to learn.

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111

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Can neural-style transfer be applied to self-driving vehicles?

AI for painting: Unraveling Neural Style Transfer

by Michael

In a world where NFT's are being sold for millions, the next profitable business might be to create unique virtual entities and who better suited for the job than artificial intelligence. In fact, well before the NFT hype, in October 2018, the first AI-generated portrait was sold for \$432,500. Since then, people have used their deep knowledge of advanced algorithms to make astounding pieces of art.

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124

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How can 5G communication be applied to autonomous driving vehicles?

**“Autonomous vehicle” Science-Research,
February 2022, Week 1
— summary from Arxiv and DOAJ**

by James

The globe is relocating into a new era with the release of 5G communication infrastructure. The concept of Intelligent Transport Systems is built around this system which is completely autonomous. This paper studies the Distributed Denial of Service attack performed over a 5G network and evaluations protection assaults, particularly the DDoS attack.

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attention-check

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How much was the author paid while working at Netflix?

Why I Quit a \$450k Engineering Job at Netflix

by Thomas

I thought I was going to stay at Netflix forever. Top of market pay. Freedom and responsibility. Unlimited PTO. What more could you ask for? So when I quit Netflix in May 2021, everyone thought I was crazy. My parents objected first. Coming from cultural revolution China where they barely had enough food to eat, they thought I was throwing away all the hard work they went through to come to America.

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102

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I implement a doubly linked list?

Linked Lists And Data Structures - What They Are And Why You Should Care.

by Michael

A few months ago I was blissfully unaware of linked lists, data structures and algorithms. However, as my graduation from a web development bootcamp draws closer I know that they'll be an important factor in determining the direction that my career path takes. If you're considering a career in software development, or even looking to level up in your career, then this article is for you.

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123

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Would there be data loss during the conversion process from JPEG to PNG?

Convert Input Image to PNG Format in Python

by John

The Cloudmersive Image API lets you make a lot of useful transformations, conversions & modifications to images using Machine Learning underneath the hood. In this article, we'll walk through how you can take advantage of the `/image/convert/to/png` iteration of this API in Python. This iteration will allow you to easily convert an image to PNG from dozens of different photo formats (visit the Cloudmersive API console for a list of all viable formats).

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119

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I use the Cloudmersive Image API to adjust the contrast ratio?

Adaptively Adjust the Contrast of an Image in Python

by Ashley

The Cloudmersive Image API includes over a dozen iterations that can help with editing images in various capacities. In this article, we'll walk through connecting to one such useful iteration in Python. This iteration uses Gamma to adaptively adjust the contrast for an input image (`/image/edit/contrast/{gamma}/adaptive`), improving the viewability and visual appeal of the image.

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130

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How is Neovim different from Vim?

Neovim for Beginners — LSP (Part 2)

by Kimberly

From the previous article, we now have a very basic LSP setup. Let's continue to enhance the configuration. This article is part of the Neovim for Beginners series. The Neovim configuration files can be found in this repository.

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114

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What was the motivation behind the Renegade Project?

The Renegade Project Brings Full-Blown Windows 11 To Smartphones

by Joshua

Microsoft abandoned Windows Phone years ago. While the lack of developer support killed it for good, its desktop-esque Continuum feature let Windows Phone owners run a limited selection of full-blown Windows apps on an external display. Today's smartphones play nice with monitors too but Microsoft had bolder ambitions: true Windows on a smartphone.

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101

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How did the inventor of the internet come up with the idea?

The Man Who Made the Internet World Possible

by Jacob

In the current times, where there is an ongoing Pandemic, and we are heavily dependent on the internet, do we exactly know: what is the internet? We would say a place where we can share information, learn more, connect with other people across the globe etc.

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125

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the pros and cons of creating a Startup with my friends?

Why you should work at a Startup

by Robert

A startup is a company in the first stages of operation. They normally expect a high growth rate fueled by multiple investment rounds starting at a pre-seed up until series C and beyond in some cases. They are characterized by being innovative and having a high failure rate estimated at 90%.

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115

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the responsibilities of a Team Lead?

3 Obvious Mistakes I Made as a Junior Team Lead

by David

I first became a Team Leader in 2019, being promoted from a Software Engineer. I had what it takes, or at least my management thought so. But nobody has ever taught me how to do this new job.

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128

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Is software engineering a more time-consuming job when compared to other jobs?

Life after career switch (from accounting to tech)

by Susan

Around the year 2016, I decided to take a leap of faith to do a career switch from accounting to tech. Ever since I made that decision, a lot of things have changed. There were ups and downs but I would definitely say it was an incredible journey. It has been a while since I posted anything and I thought that I should give an update on my progress.

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113

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some ways that I can improve my documentation?

On Living Documentation

by Matthew

Hello, today I want to talk about living documentation, having just finished the aptly-named book by Cyrille Martraire, “Living Documentation: continuous knowledge sharing by design”, published by Pearson.

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129

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Why is it important to write detailed comments?

Programmers, This is How Code Comments should Look Like

by Karen

Some people are programmers by profession. And they will undoubtedly bring more detailed answers: 1) The code comments. If you remember Zen of Python, one of the assertions is readability counts. 2)...

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117

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some good team-building strategies?

Scrum is not for Software Engineering

by Jennifer

There are plenty of managers and software engineers frustrated with Scrum. In my opinion, the fundamental difference between managers and engineers appears to be unclear understanding of each other's job.

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122

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of the piping mechanism?

Implementing Piping Mechanisms From Scratch With Python

by David

In previous tutorials, we saw how to implement high-level behavior with Dunder Methods and how the partial method offered by functools module can leverage arguments multiplicity.

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103

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some disadvantages of Terra Luna blockchain technology?

Terra Luna Could Go To 100? Best Buying Opportunity.

By [REDACTED]

We will be breaking down the Terra blockchain and the Luna token. Talking about the bull case, mid to long term. I will talk about what exactly makes the Terra blockchain so incredibly unique.

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108

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I make a model that can predict house prices?

Car price prediction — Decision Tree Regressor

by Emma

As in the previous article, I have given you an introduction to Decision Tree now I will tell you how to make a Decision Tree Regressor model in this article with some lines of codes.

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104

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some advantages and disadvantages of being a developer?

The Stages of the Great Developer Resignation — Next Stage Realisation There Is More To Life Than Work

by Matthew

The last year has seen developers resigning in great number, it didn't seem developers were resigning but taking advantage of the increased demand for developers to get better jobs for more money. Now we are reaching a new stage of the great resignation, developers getting off the hamster wheel of development and taking a break.

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How is the understandability of this article?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

120

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of network modularity?

D4S Sunday Briefing #141

by Sarah

Welcome to the Feb 6th issue of the Sunday Briefing. This week we're on hiatus from blogging, but you can catch up on our recent posts. We recently published in Medium a recap of the Top 10 Books we read in 2021, a deep dive of Community Structure and Network Modularity in the Graphs for Science substack and built a Christmas Tree Animation in the Visualization for Science substack.

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Extremely unlikely Somewhat unlikely Neither likely nor unlikely Somewhat likely Extremely likely

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107

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What is the difference between a singly linked list and a doubly linked list?

How the Doubly Linked List will fix unsolvable problems in video games and the entire world

by Madison

As I'm sure you know, the world today has a ton of social problems. Poverty, inequality, divisiveness, misinformation, all sort of predatory practices by people higher up in all kinds of power structures. What you may not know is the underlying reason for all this: Computer scientists have not yet designed the right data structure to solve these problems.

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112

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What models did Ntropy use to cluster the financial transactions?

Clustering millions of sentences to optimize the ML-workflow

by Christopher

At Ntropy, we deal with a large volume of financial transactions represented as plain text. We train models on these transactions from hundreds of businesses and financial institutions, across a range of languages and from countries around the world. Accordingly, these transactions follow a multitude of different standards and formats.

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105

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What is a typical salary for a software engineer?

Software is the New Oil

by Daniel

Even if you are not a football fan, I hope you have heard the term "Oil money". And if you are a fan of Manchester City or PSG like me, I am sure you love oil money. Haha.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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127

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I create a shell script with vim?

2 Ways to Create Custom Terminal Commands (or Aliases)

by Mary

We regularly run some terminal commands when we work on software or look at something on the network. Sometimes these commands can be annoying. I am going to explain how we can do that in 2 ways.

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109

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What is the most popular programming language?

If Programming Languages Were Disney Characters

by Olivia

Truth be told, you're never too old to enjoy Disney movies. This category of film simply has the best characters and the best plots that keep us glued to our seats even if we don't want them to, even if watching them is a total waste of time.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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126

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the current regulations for cryptocurrency?

Compliance isn't everyone's cup of tea, but it's essentially unavoidable, so let's make it as smooth as possible.

by Lisa

At Astra, we are interested in all things crypto; that's why we cannot help but take notice of the regulatory changes that the industry faces. In fact, we wanted to go one step further and make sure the DeFi platforms were not only prepared for increased compliance measures but were already tackling the challenges head-on.

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106

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of visual representation learning?

Review — MoCo: Momentum Contrast for Unsupervised Visual Representation Learning

by Emily

A dynamic dictionary with a queue and a moving-averaged encoder are built. This enables building a large and consistent dictionary on-the-fly that facilitates contrastive unsupervised learning.

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201

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of visual representation learning?

Review — MoCo: Momentum Contrast for Unsupervised Visual Representation Learning

by Jacob

A dynamic dictionary with a queue and a moving-averaged encoder are built. This enables building a large and consistent dictionary on-the-fly that facilitates contrastive unsupervised learning.

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203

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I make a model that can predict house prices?

Car price prediction — Decision Tree Regressor

by Joshua

As in the previous article, I have given you an introduction to Decision Tree now I will tell you how to make a Decision Tree Regressor model in this article with some lines of codes.

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210

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the responsibilities of a Team Lead?

3 Obvious Mistakes I Made as a Junior Team Lead

by Hannah

I first became a Team Leader in 2019, being promoted from a Software Engineer. I had what it takes, or at least my management thought so. But nobody has ever taught me how to do this new job.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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225

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How is Neovim different from Vim?

Neovim for Beginners — LSP (Part 2)

by Robert

From the previous article, we now have a very basic LSP setup. Let's continue to enhance the configuration. This article is part of the Neovim for Beginners series. The Neovim configuration files can be found in this repository.

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219

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How can 5G communication be applied to autonomous driving vehicles?

**“Autonomous vehicle” Science-Research,
February 2022, Week 1
— summary from Arxiv and DOAJ**

by Ashley

The globe is relocating into a new era with the release of 5G communication infrastructure. The concept of Intelligent Transport Systems is built around this system which is completely autonomous. This paper studies the Distributed Denial of Service attack performed over a 5G network and evaluations protection assaults, particularly the DDoS attack.

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217

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of the piping mechanism?

Implementing Piping Mechanisms From Scratch With Python

by Jennifer

In previous tutorials, we saw how to implement high-level behavior with Dunder Methods and how the partial method offered by functools module can leverage arguments multiplicity.

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205

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the steps for creating a 3D model based on a 2D image?

OpenCV python library for processing multimedia files

by Daniel

Analyzing three-dimensional data from two-dimensional images based on unnecessary noise removal, geometric transformation, contrast enhancement, and edge detection methods. Let's start installing the OpenCV python library from jupyter notebook.

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229

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some advantages and disadvantages of being a developer?

The Stages of the Great Developer Resignation — Next Stage Realisation There Is More To Life Than Work

by Karen

The last year has seen developers resigning in great number, it didn't seem developers were resigning but taking advantage of the increased demand for developers to get better jobs for more money. Now we are reaching a new stage of the great resignation, developers getting off the hamster wheel of development and taking a break.

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207

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

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Clustering millions of sentences to optimize the ML-workflow

by Madison

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208

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some ways that I can improve my documentation?

On Living Documentation

by Emma

Hello, today I want to talk about living documentation, having just finished the aptly-named book by Cyrille Martraire, “Living Documentation: continuous knowledge sharing by design”, published by Pearson.

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227

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I implement a doubly linked list?

Linked Lists And Data Structures - What They Are And Why You Should Care.

by Mary

A few months ago I was blissfully unaware of linked lists, data structures and algorithms. However, as my graduation from a web development bootcamp draws closer I know that they'll be an important factor in determining the direction that my career path takes. If you're considering a career in software development, or even looking to level up in your career, then this article is for you.

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221

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What are the current regulations for cryptocurrency?

Compliance isn't everyone's cup of tea, but it's essentially unavoidable, so let's make it as smooth as possible.

by Michael

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224

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Why is it important to write detailed comments?

Programmers, This is How Code Comments should Look Like

by James

Some people are programmers by profession. And they will undoubtedly bring more detailed answers: 1) The code comments. If you remember Zen of Python, one of the assertions is readability counts. 2)...

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215

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of network modularity?

D4S Sunday Briefing #141

by David

Welcome to the Feb 6th issue of the Sunday Briefing. This week we're on hiatus from blogging, but you can catch up on our recent posts. We recently published in Medium a recap of the Top 10 Books we read in 2021, a deep dive of Community Structure and Network Modularity in the Graphs for Science substack and built a Christmas Tree Animation in the Visualization for Science substack.

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204

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What is the most popular programming language?

If Programming Languages Were Disney Characters

by Matthew

Truth be told, you're never too old to enjoy Disney movies. This category of film simply has the best characters and the best plots that keep us glued to our seats even if we don't want them to, even if watching them is a total waste of time.

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228

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some disadvantages of Terra Luna blockchain technology?

Terra Luna Could Go To 100? Best Buying Opportunity.

by Susan

We will be breaking down the Terra blockchain and the Luna token. Talking about the bull case, mid to long term. I will talk about what exactly makes the Terra blockchain so incredibly unique.

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218

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Would there be data loss during the conversion process from JPEG to PNG?

Convert Input Image to PNG Format in Python

by Amanda

The Cloudmersive Image API lets you make a lot of useful transformations, conversions & modifications to images using Machine Learning underneath the hood. In this article, we'll walk through how you can take advantage of the `/image/convert/to/png` iteration of this API in Python. This iteration will allow you to easily convert an image to PNG from dozens of different photo formats (visit the Cloudmersive API console for a list of all viable formats).

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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223

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Is software engineering a more time-consuming job when compared to other jobs?

Life after career switch (from accounting to tech)

by John

Around the year 2016, I decided to take a leap of faith to do a career switch from accounting to tech. Ever since I made that decision, a lot of things have changed. There were ups and downs but I would definitely say it was an incredible journey. It has been a while since I posted anything and I thought that I should give an update on my progress.

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Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How is back propagation implemented in neural networks?

Training of Neural Networks — Back Propagation

by Jessica

Neural Networks are used in Deep Learning Algorithms. A neural network consists of different layers. The first layer is the input layer, the second is the various hidden layers, and finally the output layer. Initially, the input layer consists of all features that need to be passed to the neural network to learn.

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212

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some good team-building strategies?

Scrum is not for Software Engineering

by Christopher

There are plenty of managers and software engineers frustrated with Scrum. In my opinion, the fundamental difference between managers and engineers appears to be unclear understanding of each other's job.

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202

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How the Doubly Linked List will fix unsolvable problems in video games and the entire world

by Michael

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226

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How did the inventor of the internet come up with the idea?

The Man Who Made the Internet World Possible

by Lisa

In the current times, where there is an ongoing Pandemic, and we are heavily dependent on the internet, do we exactly know: what is the internet? We would say a place where we can share information, learn more, connect with other people across the globe etc.

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209

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What was the motivation behind the Renegade Project?

The Renegade Project Brings Full-Blown Windows 11 To Smartphones

by Olivia

Microsoft abandoned Windows Phone years ago. While the lack of developer support killed it for good, its desktop-esque Continuum feature let Windows Phone owners run a limited selection of full-blown Windows apps on an external display. Today's smartphones play nice with monitors too but Microsoft had bolder ambitions: true Windows on a smartphone.

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206

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Can neural style transfer be applied to self-driving vehicles?

AI for painting: Unraveling Neural Style Transfer

by Emily

In a world where NFT's are being sold for millions, the next profitable business might be to create unique virtual entities and who better suited for the job than artificial intelligence. In fact, well before the NFT hype, in October 2018, the first AI-generated portrait was sold for \$432,500. Since then, people have used their deep knowledge of advanced algorithms to make astounding pieces of art.

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211

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some security vulnerabilities that the previous version of Dart SDK had?

Dart 2.16: Improved tooling and platform handling

by Michael

Today the Dart SDK version 2.16 is available. It has no new language features, but a bunch of bug fixes (including a fix for a security vulnerability), improved support for specifying the platforms that Dart packages support, and a brand new search experience for pub.dev.

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230

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What is a typical salary for a software engineer?

Software is the New Oil

by Kimberly

Even if you are not a football fan, I hope you have heard the term "Oil money". And if you are a fan of Manchester City or PSG like me, I am sure you love oil money. Haha.

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222

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I create a shell script with vim?

2 Ways to Create Custom Terminal Commands (or Aliases)

by David

We regularly run some terminal commands when we work on software or look at something on the network. Sometimes these commands can be annoying. I am going to explain how we can do that in 2 ways.

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220

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the pros and cons of creating a Startup with my friends?

Why you should work at a Startup

by Sarah

A startup is a company in the first stages of operation. They normally expect a high growth rate fueled by multiple investment rounds starting at a pre-seed up until series C and beyond in some cases. They are characterized by being innovative and having a high failure rate estimated at 90%.

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214

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I use the Cloudmersive Image API to adjust the contrast ratio?

Adaptively Adjust the Contrast of an Image in Python

by Joshua

The Cloudmersive Image API includes over a dozen iterations that can help with editing images in various capacities. In this article, we'll walk through connecting to one such useful iteration in Python. This iteration uses Gamma to adaptively adjust the contrast for an input image (`/image/edit/contrast/{gamma}/adaptive`), improving the viewability and visual appeal of the image.

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310

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of network modularity?

D4S Sunday Briefing #141

by Hannah

Welcome to the Feb 6th issue of the Sunday Briefing. This week we're on hiatus from blogging, but you can catch up on our recent posts. We recently published in Medium a recap of the Top 10 Books we read in 2021, a deep dive of Community Structure and Network Modularity in the Graphs for Science substack and built a Christmas Tree Animation in the Visualization for Science substack.

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303

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some ways that I can improve my documentation?

On Living Documentation

by Joshua

Hello, today I want to talk about living documentation, having just finished the aptly-named book by Cyrille Martraire, “Living Documentation: continuous knowledge sharing by design”, published by Pearson.

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How the Doubly Linked List will fix unsolvable problems in video games and the entire world

by Mary

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305

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the responsibilities of a Team Lead?

3 Obvious Mistakes I Made as a Junior Team Lead

by Daniel

I first became a Team Leader in 2019, being promoted from a Software Engineer. I had what it takes, or at least my management thought so. But nobody has ever taught me how to do this new job.

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322

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How do I implement a doubly linked list?

Linked Lists And Data Structures - What They Are And Why You Should Care.

by David

A few months ago I was blissfully unaware of linked lists, data structures and algorithms. However, as my graduation from a web development bootcamp draws closer I know that they'll be an important factor in determining the direction that my career path takes. If you're considering a career in software development, or even looking to level up in your career, then this article is for you.

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319

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Why is it important to write detailed comments?

Programmers, This is How Code Comments should Look Like

by Ashley

Some people are programmers by profession. And they will undoubtedly bring more detailed answers: 1) The code comments. If you remember Zen of Python, one of the assertions is readability counts. 2)...

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318

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Is software engineering a more time-consuming job when compared to other jobs?

Life after career switch (from accounting to tech)

by Amanda

Around the year 2016, I decided to take a leap of faith to do a career switch from accounting to tech. Ever since I made that decision, a lot of things have changed. There were ups and downs but I would definitely say it was an incredible journey. It has been a while since I posted anything and I thought that I should give an update on my progress.

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323

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some disadvantages of Terra Luna blockchain technology?

Terra Luna Could Go To 100? Best Buying Opportunity.

by John

We will be breaking down the Terra blockchain and the Luna token. Talking about the bull case, mid to long term. I will talk about what exactly makes the Terra blockchain so incredibly unique.

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How is the understandability of this article?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

329

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What is the most popular programming language?

If Programming Languages Were Disney Characters

by Karen

Truth be told, you're never too old to enjoy Disney movies. This category of film simply has the best characters and the best plots that keep us glued to our seats even if we don't want them to, even if watching them is a total waste of time.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

Extremely unlikely Somewhat unlikely Neither likely nor unlikely Somewhat likely Extremely likely

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309

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I use the Cloudmersive Image API to adjust the contrast ratio?

Adaptively Adjust the Contrast of an Image in Python

by Olivia

The Cloudmersive Image API includes over a dozen iterations that can help with editing images in various capacities. In this article, we'll walk through connecting to one such useful iteration in Python. This iteration uses Gamma to adaptively adjust the contrast for an input image (`/image/edit/contrast/{gamma}/adaptive`), improving the viewability and visual appeal of the image.

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315

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the pros and cons of creating a Startup with my friends?

Why you should work at a Startup

by David

A startup is a company in the first stages of operation. They normally expect a high growth rate fueled by multiple investment rounds starting at a pre-seed up until series C and beyond in some cases. They are characterized by being innovative and having a high failure rate estimated at 90%.

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325

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What is a typical salary for a software engineer?

Software is the New Oil

by Robert

Even if you are not a football fan, I hope you have heard the term "Oil money". And if you are a fan of Manchester City or PSG like me, I am sure you love oil money. Haha.

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312

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of the piping mechanism?

Implementing Piping Mechanisms From Scratch With Python

by Christopher

In previous tutorials, we saw how to implement high-level behavior with Dunder Methods and how the partial method offered by functools module can leverage arguments multiplicity.

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302

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What models did Ntropy use to cluster the financial transactions?

Clustering millions of sentences to optimize the ML-workflow

by Michael

At Ntropy, we deal with a large volume of financial transactions represented as plain text. We train models on these transactions from hundreds of businesses and financial institutions, across a range of languages and from countries around the world. Accordingly, these transactions follow a multitude of different standards and formats.

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311

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How is back propagation implemented in neural networks?

Training of Neural Networks — Back Propagation

by Michael

Neural Networks are used in Deep Learning Algorithms. A neural network consists of different layers. The first layer is the input layer, the second is the various hidden layers, and finally the output layer. Initially, the input layer consists of all features that need to be passed to the neural network to learn.

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307

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some good team-building strategies?

Scrum is not for Software Engineering

by Madison

There are plenty of managers and software engineers frustrated with Scrum. In my opinion, the fundamental difference between managers and engineers appears to be unclear understanding of each other's job.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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304

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What was the motivation behind the Renegade Project?

The Renegade Project Brings Full-Blown Windows 11 To Smartphones

by Matthew

Microsoft abandoned Windows Phone years ago. While the lack of developer support killed it for good, its desktop-esque Continuum feature let Windows Phone owners run a limited selection of full-blown Windows apps on an external display. Today's smartphones play nice with monitors too but Microsoft had bolder ambitions: true Windows on a smartphone.

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324

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some advantages and disadvantages of being a developer?

The Stages of the Great Developer Resignation — Next Stage Realisation There Is More To Life Than Work

by James

The last year has seen developers resigning in great number, it didn't seem developers were resigning but taking advantage of the increased demand for developers to get better jobs for more money. Now we are reaching a new stage of the great resignation, developers getting off the hamster wheel of development and taking a break.

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314

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How can 5G communication be applied to autonomous driving vehicles?

**“Autonomous vehicle” Science-Research,
February 2022, Week 1
— summary from Arxiv and DOAJ**

by Joshua

The globe is relocating into a new era with the release of 5G communication infrastructure. The concept of Intelligent Transport Systems is built around this system which is completely autonomous. This paper studies the Distributed Denial of Service attack performed over a 5G network and evaluations protection assaults, particularly the DDoS attack.

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326

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of visual representation learning?

Review — MoCo: Momentum Contrast for Unsupervised Visual Representation Learning

by Lisa

A dynamic dictionary with a queue and a moving-averaged encoder are built. This enables building a large and consistent dictionary on-the-fly that facilitates contrastive unsupervised learning.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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313

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Would there be data loss during the conversion process from JPEG to PNG?

Convert Input Image to PNG Format in Python

by Matthew

The Cloudmersive Image API lets you make a lot of useful transformations, conversions & modifications to images using Machine Learning underneath the hood. In this article, we'll walk through how you can take advantage of the `/image/convert/to/png` iteration of this API in Python. This iteration will allow you to easily convert an image to PNG from dozens of different photo formats (visit the Cloudmersive API console for a list of all viable formats).

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316

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the current regulations for cryptocurrency?

Compliance isn't everyone's cup of tea, but it's essentially unavoidable, so let's make it as smooth as possible.

by Jessica

At Astra, we are interested in all things crypto; that's why we cannot help but take notice of the regulatory changes that the industry faces. In fact, we wanted to go one step further and make sure the DeFi platforms were not only prepared for increased compliance measures but were already tackling the challenges head-on.

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328

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I make a model that can predict house prices?

Car price prediction — Decision Tree Regressor

by Susan

As in the previous article, I have given you an introduction to Decision Tree now I will tell you how to make a Decision Tree Regressor model in this article with some lines of codes.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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330

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the steps for creating a 3D model based on a 2D image?

OpenCV python library for processing multimedia files

by Kimberly

Analyzing three-dimensional data from two-dimensional images based on unnecessary noise removal, geometric transformation, contrast enhancement, and edge detection methods. Let's start installing the OpenCV python library from jupyter notebook.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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301

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Can neural style transfer be applied to self-driving vehicles?

AI for painting: Unraveling Neural Style Transfer

by Jacob

In a world where NFT's are being sold for millions, the next profitable business might be to create unique virtual entities and who better suited for the job than artificial intelligence. In fact, well before the NFT hype, in October 2018, the first AI-generated portrait was sold for \$432,500. Since then, people have used their deep knowledge of advanced algorithms to make astounding pieces of art.

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320

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How is Neovim different from Vim?

Neovim for Beginners — LSP (Part 2)

by Sarah

From the previous article, we now have a very basic LSP setup. Let's continue to enhance the configuration. This article is part of the Neovim for Beginners series. The Neovim configuration files can be found in this repository.

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317

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I create a shell script with vim?

2 Ways to Create Custom Terminal Commands (or Aliases)

by Jennifer

We regularly run some terminal commands when we work on software or look at something on the network. Sometimes these commands can be annoying. I am going to explain how we can do that in 2 ways.

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321

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How did the inventor of the internet come up with the idea?

The Man Who Made the Internet World Possible

by Michael

In the current times, where there is an ongoing Pandemic, and we are heavily dependent on the internet, do we exactly know: what is the internet? We would say a place where we can share information, learn more, connect with other people across the globe etc.

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407

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What are some applications of the piping mechanism?

Implementing Piping Mechanisms From Scratch With Python

by Madison

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413

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Is software engineering a more time-consuming job when compared to other jobs?

Life after career switch (from accounting to tech)

by Matthew

Around the year 2016, I decided to take a leap of faith to do a career switch from accounting to tech. Ever since I made that decision, a lot of things have changed. There were ups and downs but I would definitely say it was an incredible journey. It has been a while since I posted anything and I thought that I should give an update on my progress.

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420

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What is a typical salary for a software engineer?

Software is the New Oil

by Sarah

Even if you are not a football fan, I hope you have heard the term "Oil money". And if you are a fan of Manchester City or PSG like me, I am sure you love oil money. Haha.

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426

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Can neural style transfer be applied to self-driving vehicles?

AI for painting: Unraveling Neural Style Transfer

by Lisa

In a world where NFT's are being sold for millions, the next profitable business might be to create unique virtual entities and who better suited for the job than artificial intelligence. In fact, well before the NFT hype, in October 2018, the first AI-generated portrait was sold for \$432,500. Since then, people have used their deep knowledge of advanced algorithms to make astounding pieces of art.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

Extremely unlikely Somewhat unlikely Neither likely nor unlikely Somewhat likely Extremely likely

This article contains an answer to the target question.

How in-depth do you think the article will be on its intended topic based on the first paragraph?

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412

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I create a shell script with vim?

2 Ways to Create Custom Terminal Commands (or Aliases)

by Christopher

We regularly run some terminal commands when we work on software or look at something on the network. Sometimes these commands can be annoying. I am going to explain how we can do that in 2 ways.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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410

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the pros and cons of creating a Startup with my friends?

Why you should work at a Startup

by Hannah

A startup is a company in the first stages of operation. They normally expect a high growth rate fueled by multiple investment rounds starting at a pre-seed up until series C and beyond in some cases. They are characterized by being innovative and having a high failure rate estimated at 90%.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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415

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How is Neovim different from Vim?

Neovim for Beginners — LSP (Part 2)

by David

From the previous article, we now have a very basic LSP setup. Let's continue to enhance the configuration. This article is part of the Neovim for Beginners series. The Neovim configuration files can be found in this repository.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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428

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some ways that I can improve my documentation?

On Living Documentation

by Susan

Hello, today I want to talk about living documentation, having just finished the aptly-named book by Cyrille Martraire, “Living Documentation: continuous knowledge sharing by design”, published by Pearson.

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423

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I make a model that can predict house prices?

Car price prediction — Decision Tree Regressor

by John

As in the previous article, I have given you an introduction to Decision Tree now I will tell you how to make a Decision Tree Regressor model in this article with some lines of codes.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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404

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I use the Cloumersive Image API to adjust the contrast ratio?

Adaptively Adjust the Contrast of an Image in Python

by Matthew

The Cloudmersive Image API includes over a dozen iterations that can help with editing images in various capacities. In this article, we'll walk through connecting to one such useful iteration in Python. This iteration uses Gamma to adaptively adjust the contrast for an input image (`/image/edit/contrast/{gamma}/adaptive`), improving the viewability and visual appeal of the image.

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422

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What is the difference between a singly linked list and a doubly linked list?

by David

How the Doubly Linked List will fix unsolvable problems in video games and the entire world

As I'm sure you know, the world today has a ton of social problems. Poverty, inequality, divisiveness, misinformation, all sort of predatory practices by people higher up in all kinds of power structures. What you may not know is the underlying reason for all this: Computer scientists have not yet designed the right data structure to solve these problems.

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425

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the steps for creating a 3D model based on a 2D image?

OpenCV python library for processing multimedia files

by Robert

Analyzing three-dimensional data from two-dimensional images based on unnecessary noise removal, geometric transformation, contrast enhancement, and edge detection methods. Let's start installing the OpenCV python library from jupyter notebook.

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419

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some advantages and disadvantages of being a developer?

The Stages of the Great Developer Resignation — Next Stage Realisation There Is More To Life Than Work

by Ashley

The last year has seen developers resigning in great number, it didn't seem developers were resigning but taking advantage of the increased demand for developers to get better jobs for more money. Now we are reaching a new stage of the great resignation, developers getting off the hamster wheel of development and taking a break.

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424

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What is the most popular programming language?

If Programming Languages Were Disney Characters

by James

Truth be told, you're never too old to enjoy Disney movies. This category of film simply has the best characters and the best plots that keep us glued to our seats even if we don't want them to, even if watching them is a total waste of time.

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421

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of visual representation learning?

Review — MoCo: Momentum Contrast for Unsupervised Visual Representation Learning

by Michael

A dynamic dictionary with a queue and a moving-averaged encoder are built. This enables building a large and consistent dictionary on-the-fly that facilitates contrastive unsupervised learning.

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417

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I implement a doubly linked list?

Linked Lists And Data Structures - What They Are And Why You Should Care.

by Jennifer

A few months ago I was blissfully unaware of linked lists, data structures and algorithms. However, as my graduation from a web development bootcamp draws closer I know that they'll be an important factor in determining the direction that my career path takes. If you're considering a career in software development, or even looking to level up in your career, then this article is for you.

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405

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of network modularity?

D4S Sunday Briefing #141

by Daniel

Welcome to the Feb 6th issue of the Sunday Briefing. This week we're on hiatus from blogging, but you can catch up on our recent posts. We recently published in Medium a recap of the Top 10 Books we read in 2021, a deep dive of Community Structure and Network Modularity in the Graphs for Science substack and built a Christmas Tree Animation in the Visualization for Science substack.

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416

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How did the inventor of the internet come up with the idea?

The Man Who Made the Internet World Possible

by Jessica

In the current times, where there is an ongoing Pandemic, and we are heavily dependent on the internet, do we exactly know: what is the internet? We would say a place where we can share information, learn more, connect with other people across the globe etc.

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414

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Why is it important to write detailed comments?

Programmers, This is How Code Comments should Look Like

by Joshua

Some people are programmers by profession. And they will undoubtedly bring more detailed answers: 1) The code comments. If you remember Zen of Python, one of the assertions is readability counts. 2)...

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418

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some disadvantages of Terra Luna blockchain technology?

Terra Luna Could Go To 100? Best Buying Opportunity.

by Amanda

We will be breaking down the Terra blockchain and the Luna token. Talking about the bull case, mid to long term. I will talk about what exactly makes the Terra blockchain so incredibly unique.

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406

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How is back propagation implemented in neural networks?

Training of Neural Networks — Back Propagation

by Emily

Neural Networks are used in Deep Learning Algorithms. A neural network consists of different layers. The first layer is the input layer, the second is the various hidden layers, and finally the output layer. Initially, the input layer consists of all features that need to be passed to the neural network to learn.

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403

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some advantages of the Cloudmersive Image API when compared to other image processing

tools?

Rotate an Image in Python

by Joshua

Setting up your very own image editing app or automated flow? The Cloudmersive Image API can be a big help, providing important photo-editing services among its suite of useful iterations. Using the Rotate Image iteration of the Image API (`/image/edit/rotate/{degrees}/angle`), you can rotate an image any number of degrees (values range from 0.0 to 360.0) in a few simple steps.

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How is the understandability of this article?

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Would there be data loss during the conversion process from JPEG to PNG?

Convert Input Image to PNG Format in Python

by Emma

The Cloudmersive Image API lets you make a lot of useful transformations, conversions & modifications to images using Machine Learning underneath the hood. In this article, we'll walk through how you can take advantage of the `/image/convert/to/png` iteration of this API in Python. This iteration will allow you to easily convert an image to PNG from dozens of different photo formats (visit the Cloudmersive API console for a list of all viable formats).

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429

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What was the motivation behind the Renegade Project?

The Renegade Project Brings Full-Blown Windows 11 To Smartphones

by Karen

Microsoft abandoned Windows Phone years ago. While the lack of developer support killed it for good, its desktop-esque Continuum feature let Windows Phone owners run a limited selection of full-blown Windows apps on an external display. Today's smartphones play nice with monitors too but Microsoft had bolder ambitions: true Windows on a smartphone.

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430

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the responsibilities of a Team Lead?

3 Obvious Mistakes I Made as a Junior Team Lead

by Kimberly

I first became a Team Leader in 2019, being promoted from a Software Engineer. I had what it takes, or at least my management thought so. But nobody has ever taught me how to do this new job.

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411

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the current regulations for cryptocurrency?

Compliance isn't everyone's cup of tea, but it's essentially unavoidable, so let's make it as smooth as possible.

by Michael

At Astra, we are interested in all things crypto; that's why we cannot help but take notice of the regulatory changes that the industry faces. In fact, we wanted to go one step further and make sure the DeFi platforms were not only prepared for increased compliance measures but were already tackling the challenges head-on.

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427

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What models did Ntropy use to cluster the financial

transactions?

●● Medium

**Clustering millions of sentences
to optimize the ML-workflow**

by Mary

At Ntropy, we deal with a large volume of financial transactions represented as plain text. We train models on these transactions from hundreds of businesses and financial institutions, across a range of languages and from countries around the world. Accordingly, these transactions follow a multitude of different standards and formats.

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402

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some good team-building strategies?

Scrum is not for Software Engineering

by Michael

There are plenty of managers and software engineers frustrated with Scrum. In my opinion, the fundamental difference between managers and engineers appears to be unclear understanding of each other's job.

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Extremely unlikely Somewhat unlikely Neither likely nor unlikely Somewhat likely Extremely likely

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401

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some security vulnerabilities that the previous version of Dart SDK had?

Dart 2.16: Improved tooling and platform handling

by Jacob

Today the Dart SDK version 2.16 is available. It has no new language features, but a bunch of bug fixes (including a fix for a security vulnerability), improved support for specifying the platforms that Dart packages support, and a brand new search experience for pub.dev.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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409

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How can 5G communication be applied to autonomous driving vehicles?

**“Autonomous vehicle” Science-Research,
February 2022, Week 1
— summary from Arxiv and DOAJ**

by Olivia

The globe is relocating into a new era with the release of 5G communication infrastructure. The concept of Intelligent Transport Systems is built around this system which is completely autonomous. This paper studies the Distributed Denial of Service attack performed over a 5G network and evaluations protection assaults, particularly the DDoS attack.

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509

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Why is it important to write detailed comments?

Programmers, This is How Code Comments should Look Like

by Olivia

Some people are programmers by profession. And they will undoubtedly bring more detailed answers: 1) The code comments. If you remember Zen of Python, one of the assertions is readability counts. 2)...

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524

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What was the motivation behind the Renegade Project?

The Renegade Project Brings Full-Blown Windows 11 To Smartphones

by James

Microsoft abandoned Windows Phone years ago. While the lack of developer support killed it for good, its desktop-esque Continuum feature let Windows Phone owners run a limited selection of full-blown Windows apps on an external display. Today's smartphones play nice with monitors too but Microsoft had bolder ambitions: true Windows on a smartphone.

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522

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What models did Ntropy use to cluster the financial transactions?

Clustering millions of sentences to optimize the ML-workflow

by David

At Ntropy, we deal with a large volume of financial transactions represented as plain text. We train models on these transactions from hundreds of businesses and financial institutions, across a range of languages and from countries around the world. Accordingly, these transactions follow a multitude of different standards and formats.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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520

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the steps for creating a 3D model based on a 2D image?

OpenCV python library for processing multimedia files

by Sarah

Analyzing three-dimensional data from two-dimensional images based on unnecessary noise removal, geometric transformation, contrast enhancement, and edge detection methods. Let's start installing the OpenCV python library from jupyter notebook.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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510

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How is Neovim different from Vim?

Neovim for Beginners — LSP (Part 2)

by Hannah

From the previous article, we now have a very basic LSP setup. Let's continue to enhance the configuration. This article is part of the Neovim for Beginners series. The Neovim configuration files can be found in this repository.

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506

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the current regulations for cryptocurrency?

Compliance isn't everyone's cup of tea, but it's essentially unavoidable, so let's make it as smooth as possible.

by Emily

At Astra, we are interested in all things crypto; that's why we cannot help but take notice of the regulatory changes that the industry faces. In fact, we wanted to go one step further and make sure the DeFi platforms were not only prepared for increased compliance measures but were already tackling the challenges head-on.

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513

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some disadvantages of Terra Luna blockchain technology?

Terra Luna Could Go To 100? Best Buying Opportunity.

by Matthew

We will be breaking down the Terra blockchain and the Luna token. Talking about the bull case, mid to long term. I will talk about what exactly makes the Terra blockchain so incredibly unique.

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503

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Would there be data loss during the conversion process from JPEG to PNG?

Convert Input Image to PNG Format in Python

by Joshua

The Cloudmersive Image API lets you make a lot of useful transformations, conversions & modifications to images using Machine Learning underneath the hood. In this article, we'll walk through how you can take advantage of the `/image/convert/to/png` iteration of this API in Python. This iteration will allow you to easily convert an image to PNG from dozens of different photo formats (visit the Cloudmersive API console for a list of all viable formats).

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515

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What is a typical salary for a software engineer?

Software is the New Oil

by David

Even if you are not a football fan, I hope you have heard the term "Oil money". And if you are a fan of Manchester City or PSG like me, I am sure you love oil money. Haha.

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508

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Is software engineering a more time-consuming job when compared to other jobs?

Life after career switch (from accounting to tech)

by Emma

Around the year 2016, I decided to take a leap of faith to do a career switch from accounting to tech. Ever since I made that decision, a lot of things have changed. There were ups and downs but I would definitely say it was an incredible journey. It has been a while since I posted anything and I thought that I should give an update on my progress.

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507

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I create a shell script with vim?

2 Ways to Create Custom Terminal Commands (or Aliases)

by Madison

We regularly run some terminal commands when we work on software or look at something on the network. Sometimes these commands can be annoying. I am going to explain how we can do that in 2 ways.

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514

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some advantages and disadvantages of being a developer?

The Stages of the Great Developer Resignation — Next Stage Realisation There Is More To Life Than Work

by Joshua

The last year has seen developers resigning in great number, it didn't seem developers were resigning but taking advantage of the increased demand for developers to get better jobs for more money. Now we are reaching a new stage of the great resignation, developers getting off the hamster wheel of development and taking a break.

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527

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some good team-building strategies?

Scrum is not for Software Engineering

by Mary

There are plenty of managers and software engineers frustrated with Scrum. In my opinion, the fundamental difference between managers and engineers appears to be unclear understanding of each other's job.

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519

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What is the most popular programming language?

If Programming Languages Were Disney Characters

by Ashley

Truth be told, you're never too old to enjoy Disney movies. This category of film simply has the best characters and the best plots that keep us glued to our seats even if we don't want them to, even if watching them is a total waste of time.

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516

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of visual representation learning?

Review — MoCo: Momentum Contrast for Unsupervised Visual Representation Learning

by Jessica

A dynamic dictionary with a queue and a moving-averaged encoder are built. This enables building a large and consistent dictionary on-the-fly that facilitates contrastive unsupervised learning.

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501

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How is back propagation implemented in neural networks?

Training of Neural Networks — Back Propagation

by Jacob

Neural Networks are used in Deep Learning Algorithms. A neural network consists of different layers. The first layer is the input layer, the second is the various hidden layers, and finally the output layer. Initially, the input layer consists of all features that need to be passed to the neural network to learn.

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505

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the pros and cons of creating a Startup with my friends?

Why you should work at a Startup

by Daniel

A startup is a company in the first stages of operation. They normally expect a high growth rate fueled by multiple investment rounds starting at a pre-seed up until series C and beyond in some cases. They are characterized by being innovative and having a high failure rate estimated at 90%.

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518

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I make a model that can predict house prices?

Car price prediction — Decision Tree Regressor

by Amanda

As in the previous article, I have given you an introduction to Decision Tree now I will tell you how to make a Decision Tree Regressor model in this article with some lines of codes.

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502

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of the piping mechanism?

Implementing Piping Mechanisms From Scratch With Python

by Michael

In previous tutorials, we saw how to implement high-level behavior with Dunder Methods and how the partial method offered by functools module can leverage arguments multiplicity.

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530

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of network modularity?

D4S Sunday Briefing #141

by Kimberly

Welcome to the Feb 6th issue of the Sunday Briefing. This week we're on hiatus from blogging, but you can catch up on our recent posts. We recently published in Medium a recap of the Top 10 Books we read in 2021, a deep dive of Community Structure and Network Modularity in the Graphs for Science substack and built a Christmas Tree Animation in the Visualization for Science substack.

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521

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Can neural style transfer be applied to self-driving vehicles?

AI for painting: Unraveling Neural Style Transfer

by Michael

In a world where NFT's are being sold for millions, the next profitable business might be to create unique virtual entities and who better suited for the job than artificial intelligence. In fact, well before the NFT hype, in October 2018, the first AI-generated portrait was sold for \$432,500. Since then, people have used their deep knowledge of advanced algorithms to make astounding pieces of art.

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526

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some security vulnerabilities that the previous version of Dart SDK had?

Dart 2.16: Improved tooling and platform handling

by Lisa

Today the Dart SDK version 2.16 is available. It has no new language features, but a bunch of bug fixes (including a fix for a security vulnerability), improved support for specifying the platforms that Dart packages support, and a brand new search experience for pub.dev.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

Extremely unlikely Somewhat unlikely Neither likely nor unlikely Somewhat likely Extremely likely

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504

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How can 5G communication be applied to autonomous driving vehicles?

**“Autonomous vehicle” Science-Research,
February 2022, Week 1
— summary from Arxiv and DOAJ**

by Matthew

The globe is relocating into a new era with the release of 5G communication infrastructure. The concept of Intelligent Transport Systems is built around this system which is completely autonomous. This paper studies the Distributed Denial of Service attack performed over a 5G network and evaluations protection assaults, particularly the DDoS attack.

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What are some advantages of the Cloudmersive Image API when compared to other image processing

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Rotate an Image in Python

by Susan

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Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I use the Cloudmersive Image API to adjust the contrast ratio?

Adaptively Adjust the Contrast of an Image in Python

by Karen

The Cloudmersive Image API includes over a dozen iterations that can help with editing images in various capacities. In this article, we'll walk through connecting to one such useful iteration in Python. This iteration uses Gamma to adaptively adjust the contrast for an input image (`/image/edit/contrast/{gamma}/adaptive`), improving the viewability and visual appeal of the image.

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525

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the responsibilities of a Team Lead?

3 Obvious Mistakes I Made as a Junior Team Lead

by Robert

I first became a Team Leader in 2019, being promoted from a Software Engineer. I had what it takes, or at least my management thought so. But nobody has ever taught me how to do this new job.

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523

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some ways that I can improve my documentation?

On Living Documentation

by John

Hello, today I want to talk about living documentation, having just finished the aptly-named book by Cyrille Martraire, “Living Documentation: continuous knowledge sharing by design”, published by Pearson.

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511

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How did the inventor of the internet come up with the idea?

The Man Who Made the Internet World Possible

by Michael

In the current times, where there is an ongoing Pandemic, and we are heavily dependent on the internet, do we exactly know: what is the internet? We would say a place where we can share information, learn more, connect with other people across the globe etc.

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512

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I implement a doubly linked list?

Linked Lists And Data Structures - What They Are And Why You Should Care.

by Christopher

A few months ago I was blissfully unaware of linked lists, data structures and algorithms. However, as my graduation from a web development bootcamp draws closer I know that they'll be an important factor in determining the direction that my career path takes. If you're considering a career in software development, or even looking to level up in your career, then this article is for you.

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517

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How the Doubly Linked List will fix unsolvable problems in video games and the entire world

by Jennifer

As I'm sure you know, the world today has a ton of social problems. Poverty, inequality, divisiveness, misinformation, all sort of predatory practices by people higher up in all kinds of power structures. What you may not know is the underlying reason for all this: Computer scientists have not yet designed the right data structure to solve these problems.

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627

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of the piping mechanism?

Implementing Piping Mechanisms From Scratch With Python

by Mary

In previous tutorials, we saw how to implement high-level behavior with Dunder Methods and how the partial method offered by functools module can leverage arguments multiplicity.

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622

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some good team-building strategies?

Scrum is not for Software Engineering

by David

There are plenty of managers and software engineers frustrated with Scrum. In my opinion, the fundamental difference between managers and engineers appears to be unclear understanding of each other's job.

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605

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How is Neovim different from Vim?

Neovim for Beginners — LSP (Part 2)

by Daniel

From the previous article, we now have a very basic LSP setup. Let's continue to enhance the configuration. This article is part of the Neovim for Beginners series. The Neovim configuration files can be found in this repository.

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613

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I make a model that can predict house prices?

Car price prediction — Decision Tree Regressor

by Matthew

As in the previous article, I have given you an introduction to Decision Tree now I will tell you how to make a Decision Tree Regressor model in this article with some lines of codes.

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615

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the steps for creating a 3D model based on a 2D image?

OpenCV python library for processing multimedia files

by David

Analyzing three-dimensional data from two-dimensional images based on unnecessary noise removal, geometric transformation, contrast enhancement, and edge detection methods. Let's start installing the OpenCV python library from jupyter notebook.

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617

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What models did Ntropy use to cluster the financial transactions?

Clustering millions of sentences to optimize the ML-workflow

by Jennifer

At Ntropy, we deal with a large volume of financial transactions represented as plain text. We train models on these transactions from hundreds of businesses and financial institutions, across a range of languages and from countries around the world. Accordingly, these transactions follow a multitude of different standards and formats.

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Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I create a shell script with vim?

2 Ways to Create Custom Terminal Commands (or Aliases)

by Michael

We regularly run some terminal commands when we work on software or look at something on the network. Sometimes these commands can be annoying. I am going to explain how we can do that in 2 ways.

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Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of visual representation learning?

**Review — MoCo: Momentum Contrast
for Unsupervised Visual Representation
Learning**

by Michael

A dynamic dictionary with a queue and a moving-averaged encoder are built. This enables building a large and consistent dictionary on-the-fly that facilitates contrastive unsupervised learning.

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612

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What is the difference between a singly linked list and a doubly linked list?

by Christopher

How the Doubly Linked List will fix unsolvable problems in video games and the entire world

As I'm sure you know, the world today has a ton of social problems. Poverty, inequality, divisiveness, misinformation, all sort of predatory practices by people higher up in all kinds of power structures. What you may not know is the underlying reason for all this: Computer scientists have not yet designed the right data structure to solve these problems.

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630

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the pros and cons of creating a Startup with my friends?

Why you should work at a Startup

by Kimberly

A startup is a company in the first stages of operation. They normally expect a high growth rate fueled by multiple investment rounds starting at a pre-seed up until series C and beyond in some cases. They are characterized by being innovative and having a high failure rate estimated at 90%.

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620

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the responsibilities of a Team Lead?

3 Obvious Mistakes I Made as a Junior Team Lead

by Sarah

I first became a Team Leader in 2019, being promoted from a Software Engineer. I had what it takes, or at least my management thought so. But nobody has ever taught me how to do this new job.

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How in-depth do you think the article will be on its intended topic based on the first paragraph?

	Extremely superficial	Somewhat superficial	Neither superficial nor in-depth	Somewhat in-depth	Extremely in-depth
How in-depth is this article?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

How would you rate the understandability of this writing based on its first paragraph?

	Extremely easy	Somewhat easy	Neither easy nor difficult	Somewhat difficult	Extremely difficult
How is the understandability of this article?	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

610

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What is a typical salary for a software engineer?

Software is the New Oil

by Hannah

Even if you are not a football fan, I hope you have heard the term "Oil money". And if you are a fan of Manchester City or PSG like me, I am sure you love oil money. Haha.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

Extremely unlikely

Somewhat unlikely

Neither likely nor unlikely

Somewhat likely

Extremely likely

This article contains an answer to the target question.

How in-depth do you think the article will be on its intended topic based on the first paragraph?

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608

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some disadvantages of Terra Luna blockchain technology?

Terra Luna Could Go To 100? Best Buying Opportunity.

by Emma

We will be breaking down the Terra blockchain and the Luna token. Talking about the bull case, mid to long term. I will talk about what exactly makes the Terra blockchain so incredibly unique.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

Extremely unlikely Somewhat unlikely Neither likely nor unlikely Somewhat likely Extremely likely

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618

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some ways that I can improve my documentation?

On Living Documentation

by Amanda

Hello, today I want to talk about living documentation, having just finished the aptly-named book by Cyrille Martraire, “Living Documentation: continuous knowledge sharing by design”, published by Pearson.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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624

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How do I use the Cloumersive Image API to adjust the contrast ratio?

Adaptively Adjust the Contrast of an Image in Python

by James

The Cloudmersive Image API includes over a dozen iterations that can help with editing images in various capacities. In this article, we'll walk through connecting to one such useful iteration in Python. This iteration uses Gamma to adaptively adjust the contrast for an input image (`/image/edit/contrast/{gamma}/adaptive`), improving the viewability and visual appeal of the image.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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601

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are the current regulations for cryptocurrency?

Compliance isn't everyone's cup of tea, but it's essentially unavoidable, so let's make it as smooth as possible.

by Jacob

At Astra, we are interested in all things crypto; that's why we cannot help but take notice of the regulatory changes that the industry faces. In fact, we wanted to go one step further and make sure the DeFi platforms were not only prepared for increased compliance measures but were already tackling the challenges head-on.

How likely do you think it is that the article will contain the answer to the target question?

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603

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Is software engineering a more time-consuming job when compared to other jobs?

Life after career switch (from accounting to tech)

by Joshua

Around the year 2016, I decided to take a leap of faith to do a career switch from accounting to tech. Ever since I made that decision, a lot of things have changed. There were ups and downs but I would definitely say it was an incredible journey. It has been a while since I posted anything and I thought that I should give an update on my progress.

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604

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Why is it important to write detailed comments?

Programmers, This is How Code Comments should Look Like

by Matthew

Some people are programmers by profession. And they will undoubtedly bring more detailed answers: 1) The code comments. If you remember Zen of Python, one of the assertions is readability counts. 2)...

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619

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What was the motivation behind the Renegade Project?

The Renegade Project Brings Full-Blown Windows 11 To Smartphones

by Ashley

Microsoft abandoned Windows Phone years ago. While the lack of developer support killed it for good, its desktop-esque Continuum feature let Windows Phone owners run a limited selection of full-blown Windows apps on an external display. Today's smartphones play nice with monitors too but Microsoft had bolder ambitions: true Windows on a smartphone.

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616

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Can neural style transfer be applied to self-driving vehicles?

AI for painting: Unraveling Neural Style Transfer

by Jessica

In a world where NFT's are being sold for millions, the next profitable business might be to create unique virtual entities and who better suited for the job than artificial intelligence. In fact, well before the NFT hype, in October 2018, the first AI-generated portrait was sold for \$432,500. Since then, people have used their deep knowledge of advanced algorithms to make astounding pieces of art.

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628

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

Would there be data loss during the conversion process from JPEG to PNG?

Convert Input Image to PNG Format in Python

by Susan

The Cloudmersive Image API lets you make a lot of useful transformations, conversions & modifications to images using Machine Learning underneath the hood. In this article, we'll walk through how you can take advantage of the `/image/convert/to/png` iteration of this API in Python. This iteration will allow you to easily convert an image to PNG from dozens of different photo formats (visit the Cloudmersive API console for a list of all viable formats).

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614

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What is the most popular programming language?

If Programming Languages Were Disney Characters

by Joshua

Truth be told, you're never too old to enjoy Disney movies. This category of film simply has the best characters and the best plots that keep us glued to our seats even if we don't want them to, even if watching them is a total waste of time.

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609

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some advantages and disadvantages of being a developer?

The Stages of the Great Developer Resignation — Next Stage Realisation There Is More To Life Than Work

by Olivia

The last year has seen developers resigning in great number, it didn't seem developers were resigning but taking advantage of the increased demand for developers to get better jobs for more money. Now we are reaching a new stage of the great resignation, developers getting off the hamster wheel of development and taking a break.

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625

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

What are some applications of network modularity?

D4S Sunday Briefing #141

by Robert

Welcome to the Feb 6th issue of the Sunday Briefing. This week we're on hiatus from blogging, but you can catch up on our recent posts. We recently published in Medium a recap of the Top 10 Books we read in 2021, a deep dive of Community Structure and Network Modularity in the Graphs for Science substack and built a Christmas Tree Animation in the Visualization for Science substack.

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626

Please consider the following question as you read and evaluate the article:

How is back propagation implemented in neural networks?

Training of Neural Networks — Back Propagation

by Lisa

Neural Networks are used in Deep Learning Algorithms. A neural network consists of different layers. The first layer is the input layer, the second is the various hidden layers, and finally the output layer. Initially, the input layer consists of all features that need to be passed to the neural network to learn.

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Participant Input

What do you think is the purpose of this study?

Do you have any suggestions or comments for this study?

Demographics

What is your age group?

- Under 18 years old
- 18 ~ 24 years old
- 25 ~ 34 years old
- 35 ~ 44 years old
- 45 ~ 54 years old
- 55 ~ 64 years old
- Above 64 years old
- Prefer not to answer

To which gender identity do you most identify?

- Woman

- Man
- Transgender Man
- Transgender Woman
- Non-Binary / Non-Conforming
- Not Listed
- Prefer Not to Answer

Are you of Spanish, Hispanic, or Latino origin?

- Yes
- No

Choose one or more races that you consider yourself to be

- White or Caucasian
- Black or African American
- American Indian/Native American or Alaska Native
- Asian
- Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander
- Other
- Prefer not to say

What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- Some high school or less
- High school diploma or GED
- Some college, but no degree
- Associates or technical degree
- Bachelor's degree
- Graduate or professional degree (MA, MS, MBA, PhD, JD, MD, DDS etc.)
- Prefer not to say

Which of the following best describes your current occupation?

- Student
- Educator
- Researcher
- Engineer / Developer
- Other
- Prefer Not to Answer

How many years of programming experience have you had?

Response ID

Thank you for completing this study! You are qualified to receive a \$5 payment!

For participants from MTurk, please copy and paste the Response ID into the text field on MTurk:

Response ID: **`{e://Field/ResponseID}`**

Once you have saved or entered your Response ID, click Submit to finish the survey.